

Introducing a Task Prioritization Tool in a Complex Supervisory Control Environment

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Abstract— Proficient attention allocation is a vital component of effective mission performance in complex mission scenarios. This study intends to develop an attention allocation tool for a complex supervisory control mission scenario with teams of heterogeneous robots. A task manager display with a simple first-come-first-serve (FCFS) attention allocation strategy was developed to evaluate if the tool can increase performance of the robots' operators. Three team size configurations were considered in a randomized order within-subject design across both tool and no-tool treatment conditions. The results emphasized the importance of the robot team size variable as critical in designing an effective attention allocation tool.

Index Terms —attention allocation; decision tools; supervisory control; queuing statistic; unmanned vehicles; robots.

I. INTRODUCTION

Command and Control (C2) technologies that allow operators to control multiple robots in complex mission scenarios are rapidly increasing. With the onset of these technologies, the C2 environment is changing from manual control to supervisory control where one operator supervises multiple and simultaneous robots' tasks. The main challenge of these C2 scenarios is information overload and the consequent attention allocation problem. This study evaluated the benefits of using a simple task manager display that prioritizes tasks in order of arrival across three different team size conditions.

II. BACKGROUND

Poor attention allocation has been shown to be linked to poor performance [1]. The method used by operators to allocate their attention affects performance. Research indicates that attention allocation in supervisory control occurs at particular choice points in which the operator stops interacting with the robot to determine which robot to service next; this is called the "What to do next" task [2], [12] include our tech report as a reference. In doing this task, the operator needs to determine what tasks are currently active and from the currently active tasks which task has the highest priority according to the mission requirements.

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This "What to do next" task may seem like a trivial thing to do in a simple scenario, but in complex mission scenario in which there are fast pace tasks management and asset allocation, and challenging mission requirements this easy task becomes complex. Furthermore, the information overload problem caused by the advances in technology just adds to the complexity of this supervisory scenario by creating unnecessary distractions and diverting the operators' attention to tasks that are not necessarily a priority at a given point in time.

A. Attention Allocation, Prioritization and Performance

In robot supervisory control environments, Cummings and Mitchell have shown that decreased performance is related to the operator's lack of situation awareness [3]. Moreover, switching between different tasks can lead to a decrease in performance by increasing set-up times [4]. Set-up times are described as the time that it takes to obtain the right mental model once the operator decides to serve a different task. The workload level also affects attention switching delays; high levels of workload and in some cases low levels of workload increase attention switching delays, which lead to increased system wait times and finally to poor performance in supervisory control environments [5]. Therefore selecting an effective attention allocation and prioritization strategy is critical to performance. There are four main attention allocation strategies used by operators: neglect, interaction, complexity mitigation, and switching order.

The neglect strategy affects the time that a vehicle is neglected. For example, an operator can decide to neglect the vehicle when it is being automated or decide to check on the vehicle even though there is no need for it. The interaction strategy affects the time the operator services the vehicle or the interaction time (IT). For example, an operator has the choice of interacting with the vehicle longer than required or only as long as required. The complexity mitigation strategy influences attention allocation through the use of cognitive abstraction. For example, operators form a vehicle grouping based on criteria in order to reduce the complexity of supervising all the vehicles (i.e., similarity of tasks then group all vehicles that do surveillance tasks). The switching order strategy influences the order in which unmanned vehicles (UVs) are serviced.

This strategy becomes more complex with heterogeneity of vehicles. For example, operators supervising two robots with heterogeneous tasks service vehicles on a first-come-first serve basis (FCFS) or by priority of the task or highest attribute first (HAF) strategy.

The order of service affects total time spend on the system (or Utilization Time, UT), as well as the time the queue waits to be serviced (WTQ). Whether the operator decides to use one or more of the strategies listed above depends on the complexity of the mission scenario and the operator's personal choice. The neglect and interaction strategies are simple and can be used alone when the scenarios are low in complexity or in combination with other strategies as complexity increases. On the other hand, the mitigation and order strategies allow them to manage more complex scenarios with fast pace and complex mission requirements. Research indicates that in complex situations where there is not an attention allocation tool available, humans often use complexity mitigation strategies such as performing the easiest or most important tasks first [6]. Furthermore, operators have a tendency to attend to similar tasks in succession to avoid the switching cost involved in changing to different tasks [7]. Moreover, the order in which robots are being served affects the total time that robots spend in the system, and the number of tasks waiting in the queue to be served. For example, if tasks are being served very efficiently the average number of tasks waiting in the queue will be less than if tasks are being served inefficiently. A study that compared performance between attention allocation strategies like FCFS and HAF in complex robot scenarios determined that there was no significant difference in performance between these two strategies [8]. However, the researchers warned that the results could be due to the team size variable. In this study, researchers used a team of three robots. Researchers stated that it is unlikely that a HAF strategy will result in significant performance gain and could instead lead to a significant increase in average UT if the team size is not big enough. This research presents the first indication that the team size variable can determine the efficiency of the attention allocation strategy employed.

B. Attention, Working Memory and Task Management

Attention and working memory are closely related. In order to perform complex tasks like prioritization and resource allocation, both these components of human cognition must be employed. Attention allows us to selectively process information in the environment and working memory allows us to retain task-relevant information in an accessible state over time. Most people do not maintain elaborate and optimal planning strategies for task management because they impose a high cognitive workload and resource demand. Task management in humans is characterized by the tendency to continue performing a lower priority task longer than optimal to avoid switching to a different task [8]. Complex mission scenarios with high workload conditions tend to make people more reactive than proactive. Research indicates that operators performed at degraded

levels in scenarios with multiple robots because they did not efficiently allocate their attention [7]. Errors associated with situation awareness occurred when all the necessary information was presented but the operator failed to attend to the required information [10].

Previous efforts to help the operators manage their tasks more efficiently indicate that attention allocation in operators is positively influenced by order active tasks in a visual list. [9]. SSC Pacific developed a tool that intended to help operators manage their tasks more efficiently by presenting a prioritized list of active tasks in a display. The tool was called the "task manager display." This display provided decision support for multi-task naval operations. The tool was developed to decrease the cognitive load involved in supervisory tasks on the Naval Land Attack Combat System (LACS) by representing the type and amount of work to be done in a prioritized display. The use of this tool has been shown to decrease workload and increase mission performance [11].

III. PROJECT GOALS

There is a need to develop an attention allocation tool that will inform operators of not only what tasks are active and need service but also suggests a prioritized order of tasks so that performance will be positively influenced. In doing this, the tool will replace the "What do I do next" task so that operators will no longer have to spend time identifying active tasks and determining the order in which they will be served. A simple attention allocation tool was developed utilizing a FCFS attention allocation strategy to prioritize tasks and a task manager display to represent the prioritized order of tasks to the operators. The main goal of this display design was to provide operators with situation awareness on what tasks need to be served and in which order. The display listed tasks in a top-down priority fashion; then, the task that arrived the earliest is on top of this ordered list. Moreover, the task manager displays some attention functionality so that when the task's box is clicked the location of the task in the map is highlighted.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The robot's operator performance was evaluated with and without this tool across three different team size conditions. It was hypothesized that a simple task manager display with a FIFO strategy would be enough to fulfill the requirements of the short duration, high frequency type of tasks represented in the mission scenario being evaluated.

A. Simulation Description

In order to test the performance of the task manager display, the RESCHU SP [12] test-bed was used. This test-bed was developed to evaluate supervisory control performance in a complex naval mission scenario. The test-bed includes three different robot team size conditions with equal heterogeneity (5, 7 and 9 robots). The main task in this test-bed is to protect an oil platform from imminent enemy attack. Each robot type is used for specific tasks. Then, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) automatically detect unidentified vehicles and warn the operators. Unmanned Surface

Vehicles (USVs) are used to identify vehicles detected by UAVs, and Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) are used to target vehicles identified as enemies.

The main tasks for the operators are to: 1) assign identification and targeting tasks to the automated system (called CSL), 2) confirm automated assignment by submitting the tasks, and 3) engage the video and weapon system payload once the UVs arrive at target locations. A secondary task is to avoid intersecting hazard areas by monitoring the UVs' path and diverting their path when intersecting these areas to avoid damage. Operators are instructed to avoid hazard areas when possible to avoid damaging the robots. A modified version of the RESCHU SP simulation was used to include the task manager display. See Figure 1.

Figure 1. Modified version of RESCHU SP with a task manager display. In the above figure the task is to assign a potential enemy vehicle to be identified and therefore it shows the location of the unidentified vehicle (white spot in the map).

B. Performance Measures

Queueing theory measures were used to measure performance in this study. A prototype queueing network for supervisory control in a complex supervisory control scenario was developed at SSC Pacific [13] for the RESCHU SP test-bed. In Figure 2, the circles represent servers: the operator, the CSL (automated system), and the robots all are servers. Tasks from both within the network and outside the network may arrive at a server's queue. For example, the appearance of a new unknown contact in the battle space marks the arrival of a task to the operator to identify the contact. In turn, the servers may pass tasks to each other within the network. For instance, the operator may submit tasks to an automated planning system (i.e., CSL server). Likewise, the automated system requests the operator to engage video or weapon payload on approval. The operator may also directly assign robot assets without the help of the automated system, or may simply redirect the robot's path of motion defined by the automation. Queueing theory provides quantitative tools to analyze the flow of tasks to and from each server.

In this study the following queueing measures were used to quantify server performance: system load, average wait times

of a queue on the server, average number of tasks in the system, and average total time of tasks in the system. System load has been used in the past to determine the workload on the server. This measure is a function of the arrival rate and the service rate.

Figure 2. Supervisory Control Queueing Network for RESCHU SP.

In other words, system loads constitute a measure of how fast the operator can serve the tasks that arrive at the system. Average number of tasks in the system indicates the average number of tasks that the operator serves during the entire mission scenario. If this number is low, it may be an indicator that the operator is serving tasks more efficiently and therefore the average number of tasks is smaller. Average wait times of tasks in the queue indicates the average time a task must wait to be served. Then, if average wait time is small it may indicate that in general most tasks do not wait long to be served. Finally, average total time of task in the system indicates the average total time that tasks spend in the system. This number includes both wait times and service time; again because this is a function of both those measures if this measure is high it may be an indication that tasks are not being served very efficiently.

C. Experimental Trials

A total of 60 experimental trials were conducted at SSC Pacific. The study design was a randomized within-subject design with a total of six experimental conditions (2 scenarios x 3 team size conditions). All 10 subjects underwent extended training for both the original RESCHU SP simulation without the task manager display and the simulation with the task manager display. Subjects were instructed to use the task manager display to help them allocate their attention efficiently. Performance measures were computed during the trials including: observed average number of tasks in the system (N_o), observed average total time of tasks in the system (T_o), observed average waiting time of tasks in the queue (W_o), and system load (ρ_o). These measures were used to quantify the efficiency of the human server in both conditions (with and without the task manager display).

V. RESULTS

The results of this experiment will be reported at the conference.

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